

An analytical expression of non-Nernstian catalytic mechanism at micro and macro electrodes at voltammetry

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Abstract: In this paper, the electrode surface concentration for non-Nernstian and Nernstian CT and the chemical thermodynamics is derived. This model represented a heat or partial differential equation and reconstructed changes over time in the Voltammetry chemical kinetics by using homotopy perturbation and Laplace transform method. In this closed form of analytical solutions of the concentration at electrode surface for non-Nernstian and Nernstian CT is derived. The non-Nernstian catalytic mechanism attains the steady-state, and a general transient current-potential is expressed. The influence of Sum of the electrochemical rate constants, the diffusion coefficient of species D and the steady-state current is obtained. It has a very straightforward mathematical form. The analytical results are in good agreement.

Key words: Catalytic mechanism, spherical electrode, Laplace transforms, homotopy perturbation method, Non-Nernstian electron transfer

1. Introduction

The resolution of the diffusive-kinetic problems is simple for all the reaction mechanisms [1, 2]. The chemical reactions are one of the parts of electro active species of the electrode process [3]. A catalytic process of system O/R acts as the catalyst in Scheme I [4]. The current is always more extensive than the redox couple O/R [5]. The kinetics of charge transfer is slow for solutions of the catalytic scheme [6]. To find the demonstrated the effective heterogeneous kinetics to be modified experimentally, varying the pseudo-first-order catalytic kinetics through the bulk concentrations [7]. Cyclic voltammetry is inevitable instrumental in the electrochemical laboratory because it gives chemical and mechanistic aspects [8, 9]. Surface redox systems with voltammetric techniques for all coupled chemical reactions are importance [10–13]. Square-wave voltammetry is a leading technique in voltammetric. Its unique features are applied exciting signal. [14, 15]. In recent years the micrometre dimensions are expanded of electrochemical [16–18].

Microelectrodes are used for electrochemical measurements. One boundary condition is particularly on electrode the other is an insulating portion of the boundary surrounding the electrode [19]. The works established equivalence relationships between the response at micro discs [20] given that the latter to practice through their modelling is time-consuming. We consider the unique surface regenerative process in which, since the beginning of the experiment, both electro-inactive substrates given in great abundance in electrochemical

cells [21]. A mathematical model relating to homogeneous chemical reactions at hemispherical microelectrodes in transient chronoamperometry conditions has been established. Using Duhamel's theorem, analytical solutions for species and current concentrations were obtained as the practical terms are referring to steady-state values of concentration and current approach. The solutions obtained are explicit only under current conditions that are constrained [22].

The chronoamperometric current produced the electrochemical reaction in a rotating disc electrode of non-linear diffusion equations is performed [23]. It is possible to model rotating disc electrodes with linear and non-linear convection differential mechanism equations of EC, 'EC, Disp, and ECE reactions [24]. The solutions for perturbed differential equations is the first-order impulsive neutral function. The main tools are the sum of contractions, completely continuous maps in Frechet spaces and the semi group theory [25]. Human and mosquito are affected by the Dengue virus. The treatment of this model is solved by Homotopy Perturbation Method and obtained the Numerical solutions [26]. Semi discretization in space is obtained using finite elements in space and full discrete element equation is obtained using the Crank-Nicolson scheme. Newell-WhiteheadSegel equation is applied in more fields like chemical engineering, ecology, biology and bioengineering. Then it solved numerically [27].

Figure 1: (a) Non-Nernstian catalytic mechanism [28], (b) A simple electrode reaction.

Nomenclature:

Symbols	Definitions & Units
u_ϕ	Concentration of electrode surface ($mol\ cm^{-3}$)
ϕ_N^s	Value of the ϕ -variable at the electrode surface when the chemical equilibrium is perturbed by a Nernstian charge transfer.
r	Radial coordinate(m)
D	Diffusion coefficient of species O and R (cm^2/s)
r_s	Radius of the (hemi-) spherical electrode (m)
t	Time of application of the potential pulse (s).
T	Temperature of the electrolyte solution (K).
F	Faraday constant (C/mol).
A	Electrode area (cm^2).
K	Conditional chemical equilibrium is constant of the homogeneous reaction (MS^{-1}).
I^{NN}	Current response of a catalytic mechanism with a non - Nernstian charge transfer (A).
κ	Sum of the chemical rate constants of the homogeneous reaction (MS^{-1})
k_{ox}	Kinetic constant of the oxidation of species (MS^{-1})
k_{red}	Kinetic constant of the reduction of species (MS^{-1})
k_T	Sum of the electrochemical rate constants (MS^{-1})
ρ	Over potential (V)
ξ^*	Sum of the bulk concentrations of the electroactive species (O and R).
R	Constant of ideal gases.
E	Applied potential.
I	Current response of a catalytic mechanism.
k_T^d	Dimensionless k_T referred to the thickness of the linear diffusion layer for (ultra) microelectrodes.

2. A Mathematical formulation of the problem

The linear diffusion equation is given as follow [28]:

$$\frac{\partial u_\phi}{\partial t} = D \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_\phi}{\partial r^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

The boundary condition is

$$\begin{aligned} u_\phi &= 0 \text{ at } t = 0 \\ u_\phi &= 0 \text{ as } r \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial u_\phi(r, t)}{\partial r} \right)_{r=r_s} = \frac{u_\phi^s}{r_s} + \frac{k_T}{D} (u_\phi^s - u_{\phi N}^s) \quad (3)$$

Where, u_ϕ^s are the value of u_ϕ , k_T is sum of the electrochemical kinetic constants. So, the boundary condition (3) will be written as follows.

$$\left(\frac{\partial u_\phi(r, t)}{\partial r} \right)_{r=r_s} = \frac{u_\phi}{r_s} + \frac{k_T}{D} (u_\phi - u_{\phi N}^s) \quad (4)$$

$$k_T = k_{red} + k_{ox} \quad (5)$$

$$\phi_N^s = \xi^* \frac{1 - K e^\eta}{1 + e^\eta} e^\chi, \chi = \kappa t, \eta = \frac{F}{RT} (E - E^0) \quad (6)$$

The current is defined as

$$\frac{1}{FAD} = \frac{e^{-\chi}}{1 + K} \left(\frac{u_\phi^s}{r_s} - \left(\frac{\partial u_\phi(r, t)}{\partial r} \right)_{r=r_s} \right) \quad (7)$$

where r_s is radius of the spherical electrode, D diffusion coefficient of species O and R, K is equilibrium constant, k_{ox} is the kinetic constant of the oxidation of species R to O, k_{red} is a kinetic constant of the reduction of species O to R, T is Temperature, R is constant of ideal gases and F is Faraday constant.

3. Derivation of concentrations using HPM and Laplace transform method and analytical solution of current

In this study, the Non-Nernstian catalytic mechanism at the electrodes of mass transport. The differential equations solved by using the homotopy perturbation and Laplace transform methods.

To find the solution of equation (1) take Laplace transformation.

$$\frac{d^2 \bar{u}_\phi}{dr^2} - \left(\frac{1}{D} \right) (s\bar{u}_\phi(r, s) - u_\phi(r, 0)) = 0 \quad (8)$$

The boundary conditions are as follow:

$$u_\phi(r, 0) = 0 \text{ at } t = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{u}_\phi(r, s) = 0 \text{ as } r \rightarrow \infty \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_\phi(r, t)}{\partial r} = \left(\frac{u_\phi}{r_s} + \frac{k_T}{D} u_\phi \right) - \frac{1}{s} \frac{k_T}{D} u_{\phi N}^s \text{ at } r = r_s \quad (11)$$

Using the boundary condition (9) in equation (8) we write

$$\frac{d^2 \bar{u}_\phi(r, s)}{dr^2} - \frac{s\bar{u}_\phi(r, s)}{D} = 0 \quad (12)$$

Construct the homotopy perturbation method in equation (12) as follows:

$$(1-p) \left[\frac{d^2 \bar{u}_\phi(r, s)}{dr^2} - \frac{s\bar{u}_\phi(r, s)}{D} \right] + p \left[\frac{d^2 \bar{u}_\phi(r, s)}{dr^2} - \frac{s\bar{u}_\phi(r, s)}{D} \right] = 0 \quad (13)$$

The approximate solutions of equation (13) are

$$\bar{u}_\phi(r, s) = \bar{u}_{\phi_0}(r, s) + p\bar{u}_{\phi_1}(r, s) + p^2\bar{u}_{\phi_2}(r, s) + \dots \quad (14)$$

Replacing equation (14) with equation (13), and equate the terms of p^0 , we obtain

$$p^0 : \frac{d^2 \bar{u}_\phi(r, s) + p\bar{u}_{\phi_1}(r, s) + \dots}{dr^2} - \frac{s\bar{u}_\phi(r, s) + p\bar{u}_{\phi_1}(r, s) + \dots}{D} = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$p^0 : \frac{d^2 \bar{u}_\phi(r, s)}{dr^2} - \frac{s\bar{u}_\phi(r, s)}{D} = 0 \quad (16)$$

Solving the above differential equation

$$\bar{u}_\phi(r, s) = C_1 e^{\sqrt{\frac{s}{D}}r} + C_2 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{s}{D}}r} \quad (17)$$

Using the conditions in equations (10) and (11) we get the concentration

$$u_\phi(r, t) = \frac{k_T u_{\phi N}^s}{\sqrt{D} \left(\frac{\sqrt{D}}{r_s} + \frac{k_T}{\sqrt{D}} \right)} \left[-e^{\left(\frac{\sqrt{D}}{r_s} + \frac{k_T}{\sqrt{D}} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\sqrt{D}}{r_s} + \frac{k_T}{\sqrt{D}} \right) t - \frac{(r-r_s)}{\sqrt{D}} \right)} \left\{ \operatorname{erfc} \left(\left(\frac{\sqrt{D}}{r_s} + \frac{k_T}{\sqrt{D}} \right) \sqrt{t} + \frac{r-r_s}{2\sqrt{Dt}} \right) \right\} + \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{r-r_s}{2\sqrt{Dt}} \right) \right] \quad (18)$$

The current equation is

$$\frac{I^{NN}}{FAD} = \frac{e^{-\chi}(1 - Ke^\eta)}{(1 + e^\eta)(1 + K)} \left[\frac{k_T^d}{(1 + k_T^d)r_s} - \frac{k_T e^\chi \left(D + k_T r_s e^{\frac{(D+k_T r_s)^2 t}{r_s^2 D}} \left(1 - \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{(D+k_T r_s)\sqrt{t}}{r_s \sqrt{D}} \right) \right) \right)}{D(D + k_T r_s)} \right] \quad (19)$$

Figure 2: The concentration of versus time it denotes equation (18)

Figure 3: Normalised current versus the potential for the different values of the parameters denotes equation (18)

Figure 4: steady state current versus the potential for the different values of the parameters

Figure 5: A steady-state for non-Nernstian CT

4. Results and discussion

The partial differential Equation (17) solving analytical solution for the concentrations of electrodes of mass transport using Homotopy perturbation and Laplace transform methods. Equation (18) represents the closed approximate analytical solution of the current. The concentration of u_ϕ with time t are expressed in Figures (2.a)-(2.c).

In Figures (2.a), (2.b) and (2.c), shows the concentration of electrodes of mass transport. Then the values of k_T , D and η , We noticed that the concentration increases as the value of parameters are increasing. Diffusion control is the reaction of the electrochemical rate constants and the diffusion coefficient of species. When the module is large, high catalytic activity and active membrane thickness are observed or at low reaction rate constant or diffusion coefficient values are determined by enzyme reaction and diffusion properties of the reactants.

Figures (3.a) and (3.b) represented the electrochemical rate constants and equilibrium constant of the homogeneous reaction. The parameter k_T and K is inferred that the current density increases as the dimensionless potential increase. Figure (3.c) illustrates the dimensionless current density versus potential for various values of the parameter D . The current density increases as the dimensionless parameter decreases. Figures (3.d) and (3.e) denotes the thickness of the linear diffusion layer for microelectrodes increases with increase of the enzyme concentration as well as with decrease of the diffusivity of increasing potential. Figure (3.e), where we calculate that the waves shift towards negative potentials as χ becomes high. From Figure (3.f), it is observed that the value of u_ϕ decreases the radius of spherical electrode r_s decreases.

Steady-state current versus the potential for the different values of the parameters D, r_s, k_T^d, t, χ and k_T . Figures (4.a) to (4.f) represented the diffusion coefficient, radius of the spherical electrode, the thickness of the linear diffusion layer for microelectrodes, chemical rate constants of the homogeneous reaction with time. The concentration profiles for different values of D, r_s, k_T^d, t, k_T are shown in Figures (4.a), (4.b), (4.c), (4.d) and (4.f), where it is observed that a decreases. The parameters D, r_s, k_T^d, t, k_T leads to a decrease in concentration. The effect of the parameter (k_T) on the concentration is directly opposite to that of other parameters showed in Figure (4.e). Its mean, a values of k_T decrease when concentration is increase. It shows the answer to FDA at different frequencies of a 6MM cysteine solution. The separate pre-wave merges into the FDA oxidation wave compatible. when the CV data frequency is high.

This situation is similar to the normal mechanism $O + e^- \rightleftharpoons R$ is reported by Oldham [29]. A steady-state for non-Nernstian CT is denoted by Figure 5. Also, k_1 and k_2 , once the value of K is known, can also be found from the current limit values. Where the SSV responses were normalised with respect to a simple CT's cathode limiting current. Chemical catalysis is always increasing due to the equilibrium constant K.

5. conclusion

A non-linear time-independent equation is solved using Homotopy perturbation and Laplace transform methods. The primary result of this work is calculations of concentration of u_ϕ and current for the kinetic scheme. They are also presented for the steady-state current analytically, and the transient of the current-potential reactions of the chemically reversible first-order catalytic mechanism has been deduced. Current-potential curves can be linearized as in the case of reversible and irreversible transfers of charges, but not when the transfer of electrons is quasi-reversible. Therefore, the quicker the catalysis, the less reversible the electrochemical activity would be, or the smaller the electrode. The theoretical solutions used in both direct-current and differential techniques and it is the simplest accurate solution for the concentration and current. The Homotopy perturbation method is a possible method to solve other non-linear equations.

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